

New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Triangle-free search Edge

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1 SYNOPSIS

In this scientific research, (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_s\}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned} & |(\sum_{E_i \in A_s} T(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in A_s} I(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in A_s} F(E_i))| \\ &= \max_{B_s \subseteq E_{NSHG}} |\{ (\sum_{E_i \in B_s} T(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in B_s} I(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in B_s} F(E_i)) | \\ &\quad \forall E_i, E_j, E_k \in B_s : \\ &\quad V_a \in E_i, E_j \ \& \ V_b \in E_j, E_k \not\Rightarrow V_c \in E_i, E_k \\ &\quad \}|. \end{aligned}$$

In this scientific research, new configurations are introduced for the new SuperHyperNotions, namely a Triangle-free search Edge and a Neutrosophic Triangle-free search Edge. Two different SuperHyperDefinitions were started for them, but research has progressed and SuperHyperNotion, SuperHyperUniform, and SuperHyperClass are well-defined and well-reviewed based on them. Literature review is implemented throughout this research. To shine the light and importance of this research, a comparison between this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions and basic SuperHyperNumbers is presented. Definitions are followed by examples and examples, so clarifications are guided by various tools. Applications are designed to understand the theoretical aspect of this ongoing research. “Cancer diagnosis” are the things that are being researched to explore the challenges that make sense in ongoing research and future research. It is a special case. Cells are viewed in the intended manner. There are different types of them. Some are individual and some are well modeled by groups of cells. All these types are officially called “SuperHyperVertex”, but the relationships between them all are officially called “SuperHyperEdge”. “SuperHyperGraph” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” frameworks are selected and selected for research on “Cancer Diagnosis”. Thus, these complex and dense super-hypermodels open avenues for research on theoretical aspects and “cancer diagnosis”. Ways to pursue this scientific research have been considered. It has also been formally collected in the form of several questions and problems. It is useful to define a “neutrosophic” version of Triangle-free search Edge. Since there are more ways to get type results a Triangle-free search Edge becomes more understandable. In order to master the Neutrosophic Triangle-free search Edge, there is a need to “re-define” the concept of “Triangle-free search Edge mastery”. SuperHyperVertices and

SuperHyperEdges are assigned by alphabetical labels. In this method, the position of tags is used to assign values. Suppose a Triangle-free search Edge. If the specified table contains “values of vertices, supervertices, edges, hyperedges, and hyperedges belonging to Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” with key points, it is redefined. ”values of vertices & number of positions in alphabet”, ”Values of SuperVertices&maximum values of its vertices”, ”values of edges&maximum values of its vertices”, ”super edge values&max values of its vertices”, “super edge values” and maximum values of its endpoints”. To get examples and structural examples, I would like to introduce the next SuperHyperClass SuperHyperGraph based on Triangle-free search Edge. This is the original. Having the foundation of the previous definition in the SuperHyperClass type would be disciplined. If there is a need to have all Triangle-free search Edge until Triangle-free search Edge, then it is officially called “Triangle-free search Edge”, but otherwise, it is not Triangle-free search Edge. There is some explanation for the original definition titled “Triangle-free search Edge”. These two examples are further explored and distinguished because they are characterized in the SuperHyperClass disciplinary methods based on a dominant Triangle-free search Edge. Because of having Triangle-free search Edge, there is a need to “re-define” the concept of “neutrosophic Triangle-free search Edge” and “neutrosophic Triangle-free search Edge”. SuperHyperVertices and SuperHyperEdges are assigned by alphabetical labels. In this method, the position of tags is used to assign values. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” is redefined if the desired table exists. And if the desired table exists, a Triangle-free search Edge is redefined to a “Neutrosophic Triangle-free search Edge”. It is useful to define a “Neutrosophic” version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there are more ways to obtain Neutrosophic type results, a SuperHyper- Neutrosophic Triangle-free search Edge becomes more understandable. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. If the desired table exists, there are a number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses. So are SuperHyperPath, SuperHyperCycle, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite and SuperHyperWheel. ”Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel”. A graph is SuperHyperUniform if it is a SuperHyperGraph and the number of SuperHyperEdges elements is the same. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are a number of SuperHyperClasses as follows. It is a SuperHyperPath if there is only one SuperVertex as an intersection between two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions. If only one SuperVertex is given as an intersection between two SuperHyperEdges, it is SuperHyperCycle. It is SuperHyperStar and only one SuperVertex as intersection among all SuperHyperEdges. It is SuperHyperBipartite, and only one SuperVertex is given as the intersection between two SuperHyperEdges, and these SuperVertices, which form two distinct sets, have no SuperHyperEdge in common. This is SuperHyperMultiPartite. Only one SuperVertex is given as an intersection between two SuperHyperEdges, and these SuperVertices, which form separate multisets, have no SuperHyperEdge in common. If only one SuperHyperEdge among the given two SuperHyperEdges is a SuperHyperWheel and a SuperVertex has a SuperHyperEdge with any regular SuperVertex. SuperHyperModel suggests specific designs and specific architectures. SuperHyperModel is officially called “SuperHyperGraph” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”. In this SuperHyperModel, the “special” cells and the “special group” of cells are SuperHyperModeled as “SuperHyperVertices” and the common and desired properties between the “special” cells and the “special group” of cells. SuperHyperModeled as “SuperHyperEdges”. Sometimes, to have a more accurate SuperHyperModel, it is useful to have some degree of determinism, uncertainty, and neutrality, in this case the SuperHyperModel is called “Neutrosophic”. In future scientific research, the foundation will be based on “diagnosis

of cancer” and the results and definitions will be introduced in redeemed methods. Cancer diagnosis in long-term practice. The specific region is assigned by the model (called SuperHyperGraph) and the long cycle of movement of the cancer is determined by this scientific research. Sometimes the movement of cancer is not easy to detect, because there is certainty, uncertainty and neutrality about the movements and effects of cancer on that area. This event leads us to choose another model [which is said to be the Neutrosophic superhypergraph] in order to have a proper understanding of what happened and was done. There are some specific models, which are well known and have names, and some SuperHyperGeneral SuperHyperModels. The movements and effects of cancer in complex pathways and between complex groups of cells can be visualized with a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (-/SuperHyperCycle, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The goal is to find the longest Triangle-free search Edge or the strongest Triangle-free search Edge in those Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels. Some general results are presented for the longest Triangle-free search Edge called Triangle-free search Edge and the strongest Triangle-free search Edge called Neutrosophic Triangle-free search Edge. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible SuperHyperPaths have only two SuperHyperEdges, but it is not enough as having at least three SuperHyperEdges is necessary to form any style of cycle. There is no form of any cycle, but literally, it is the transformation of any cycle. It literally transforms and does not form. A basic introduction to the theory of Triangle-free search Edge Neutrosophic, SuperHyperGraphs and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs is suggested.

Keywords: Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, SuperHyper^{Triangle-free search Edge}, Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition

AMS Subject Classification: 05C17, 05C22, 05E45

2 Applied Notions Under The Scrutiny Of The Motivation Of This Scientific Research

In this scientific research, there are ideas in the prominent frameworks of motivations. I try to bring motivations in narrative ways. Some Cells have faced attacks from the established situation with cancer attacks in this case, there is some analysis embedded in the case current situations where cells can be labeled as some groups and some groups or individuals are overlabeled, all from behaviors to overcome cancer attacks. In embedded situations, cell individuals and cell groups can be considered as “new groups”. So it encourages us to find suitable SuperHyperModels for more appropriate analysis about this dirty story. I found SuperHyperModels, officially called “SuperHyperGraphs” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. In this SuperHyperModel, cells and groups of cells are defined as “SuperHyperVertices” and relationships between individual cells and groups of cells are defined as “SuperHyperEdges”. So this is another motivation for us to do research on this SuperHyperModel based on “cancer diagnosis”. Sometimes, things get worse. The situation has passed certainty and precise style. So it is beyond them. There are three descriptions, i.e., degrees of determination, uncertainty, and neutrality, for any object based on ambiguous forms, i.e., incomplete data, imprecise data, and uncertain analysis. The second model can be considered in the previous SuperHyperModel. This is SuperHyperModel. This is SuperHyperGraph but officially called “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Cancer is a disease, but the model is supposed to understand what happens in this phenomenon. The special case of this disease is considered and some parameters are used as consequences of the model. Cells are attacked by the disease, but the movement of cancer is in a specific area. Knowing the mind of cancer can help to find some cures for this disease. SuperHyperGraph and

Neutrosophic Super-HyperGraph are super-hypermodels used in “cancer diagnosis” and both are the foundation of the background of this scientific research. Sometimes cancer has occurred in an area full of cells, cell groups, and embedded styles. In this section, SuperHyperModel proposes based on the links of cancer movements in the form of unity styles with the formation of design and architecture officially called “Triangle-free search Edge”, in the themes of specialized terms and common words. Particle for direct object. Applied concepts under the investigation of the motivation of this scientific research. The “SuperHyper” prefix refers to the theme of embedded styles for background discovery for SuperHyperNotions. Cancer diagnosis in long-term practice. The specific region is assigned by the model (called SuperHyperGraph) and the long cycle of movement of the cancer is determined by this scientific research. Sometimes the movement of Cancer is not easy to identify because there is certainty, uncertainty and neutrality about the movements and effects of Cancer in that region. This event leads us to choose another model [said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph]. Easy understanding of what happened and what was done. There are some specific models that are well known and named and some general models. The movements and effects of cancer in complex pathways and between complex groups of cells can be visualized by a neutrosophic superhyperpath (-/SuperHyperCycle, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The goal is to find Triangle-free search Edge or Neutrosophic Triangle-free search Edge for SuperHyperModels in it. Some general results are presented. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths have only two SuperHyperEdges, but it is not enough as having at least three SuperHyperEdges is necessary to form any style of cycle. There is no form of cycle, but it is literally a form of any cycle. It literally transforms and does not form.

Question 2.1. *How to define “SuperHyperNotions and to do research” to find the “Triangle-free search Edge Rate” of any cell or groups of cells based on fixed cell or fixed group of cells broadly, “Triangle-free search Edge Rate” based on fixed groups or fixed cells. Groups of groups of cells?*

Question 2.2. *What are the best descriptions for “diagnosing cancer” in terms of these chaotic and dense super-hypermodels in which embedded concepts are depicted?*

This motivation to find concepts to use in this dense model is called “SuperHyperGraphs”. So it motivates us to define different types of “Triangle-free search Edge” and “neutrosophic Triangle-free search Edge” over “superhypergraph” and “neutrosophic superhypergraph”. Then this scientific research has taken more motivations to define SuperHyperClasses and find some connections among this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions. It motivates us to obtain examples and examples to clarify the framework of this scientific research. The general results and some of the results about some of the connections are the ways that the key point of this scientific research, “diagnosis of cancer” is more understandable and clear.

The framework of this research is as follows. First, I will introduce the basic definitions to clarify the basics. In the “Introductions” subsection, basic definitions about SuperHyperGraphs and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are introduced and discussed in depth. Basic concepts are thoroughly explained and illustrated, and sometimes a literature review is used to make sense of what is to come in the coming sections. The main definitions and their explanations, along with some results on the new concepts, Triangle-free search Edge and Neutrosophic Triangle-free search Edge, are specified in the sections “Triangle-free search Edge” and “Neutrosophic Triangle-free search Edge”. In the concept of dealing with results and in Triangle-free search Edge to create logic about the continuation of the scientific research, the ideas of SuperHyperUniform and Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform are introduced and as their

consequences, the corresponding SuperHyperClasses are specified to summarize the work done in this section, as “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”. Going back to the core concepts, clever steps towards common concepts to extend new concepts in new frameworks, SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, in “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses” sections. There is the initial scientific research on supergeneral relations and as the final and final part of the theoretical scientific research is available in the section “General results”. Some general SuperHyperRelations are fundamental and are known as fundamental SuperHyperNotions, as in “General results” were extracted and discussed. “Triangle-free search Edge”, “Neutrosophic Triangle-free search Edge”, “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”. There are curious questions about what has been done about SuperHyperNotions to make sense of the superiority of this scientific research and to discover the word “best” as a description and adjective of this scientific research as presented in the “Triangle-free search Edge” section. The keyword of this scientific research was presented in the section “Applications in cancer diagnosis” with two cases and sub-sections “Case 1: Initial steps towards SuperHyperBipartite as SuperHyperModel” and “Case 2: Incremental steps towards SuperHyperMultiperdel as SuperHyper”. In the “open issues” section, there is a detailed examination and recognition of what was done in this scientific research and what happened in this scientific research in the form of “questions” and “issues” in order to understand this scientific research in an outstanding style, the advantages and limitations of this scientific research in addition to What has been done in this scientific research is stated in the “conclusion and final remarks” section.

3 Neutrosophic Preliminaries Of This Scientific Research On the Redeemed Ways

In this section, the basic material in this scientific research, is referred to [Single Valued Neutrosophic Set](**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.2,p.2), [Neutrosophic Set](**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.1,p.1), [Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.5,p.2), [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.7,p.3), [t-norm](**Ref. [1]**, Definition 2.7, p.3), and [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.7,p.3), [Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths] (**Ref. [1]**,Definition 5.3,p.7), and [Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)] (**Ref. [1]**,Definition 5.4,p.7). Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are addressed to **Ref. [1]**.

In this subsection, the basic material which is used in this scientific research, is presented. Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are elicited.

Definition 3.1 (Neutrosophic Set). (**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.1,p.1).

Let X be a Eulerian-Path-Cut of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x ; then the **Neutrosophic set** A (NS A) is an object having the form

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$$

where the functions $T, I, F : X \rightarrow]-0, 1^+[$ define respectively the a **truth-membership function**, an **indeterminacy-membership function**, and a **falsity-membership function** of the element $x \in X$ to the set A with the condition

$$-0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3^+.$$

The functions $T_A(x)$, $I_A(x)$ and $F_A(x)$ are real standard or nonstandard subsets of $]^{-0}, 1^+]$.

Definition 3.2 (Single Valued Neutrosophic Set). (Ref. [1], Definition 2.2, p.2).

Let X be a Eulerian-Path-Cut of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x . A **single valued Neutrosophic set** A (SVNS A) is characterized by truth-membership function $T_A(x)$, an indeterminacy-membership function $I_A(x)$, and a falsity-membership function $F_A(x)$. For each point x in X , $T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \in [0, 1]$. A SVNS A can be written as

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}.$$

Definition 3.3. The **degree of truth-membership**, **indeterminacy-membership** and **falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$T_A(X) = \min[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = \min[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$\text{and } F_A(X) = \min[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$$

Definition 3.4. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{ x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0 \}.$$

Definition 3.5 (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [1], Definition 2.5, p.2).

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where

- (i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ;
- (ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ;
- (iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'})) : T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (vii) $\sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (viii) $\sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (ix) and the following conditions hold:

$$T'_V(E_{i'}) \leq \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$I'_V(E_{i'}) \leq \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$\text{and } F'_V(E_{i'}) \leq \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}}$$

where $i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$.

Figure 1. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_V(E_{i'})$, $T''_V(E_{i'})$, and $T'''_V(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the ii' th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Example 3.6. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic notion, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint.
- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic notion, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint.
- On the Figure (3), the SuperHyperNotion, namely, SuperHyperGirth, is up. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 .

Figure 2. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 3. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 4. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

- On the Figure (4), there is no empty SuperHyperEdge but E_3 is a loop SuperHyperEdge on $\{F\}$ and there are some SuperHyperEdges, namely, E_1 on $\{H, V_1, V_3\}$, alongside E_2 on $\{O, H, V_4, V_3\}$ and E_4, E_5 on $\{N, V_1, V_2, V_3, F\}$. 280
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- On the Figure (5), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 283
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- On the Figure (6), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 285
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- On the Figure (7), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 287
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- On the Figure (8), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 289
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- On the Figure (9), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 291
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- On the Figure (10), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 293
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- On the Figure (11), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 295
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- On the Figure (12), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 297
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- On the Figure (13), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 299
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- On the Figure (14), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 301
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- On the Figure (15), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 303
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Figure 5. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs mentioned as the SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 6. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 7. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs depicted SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 8. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with dense SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 9. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a messy SuperHyper-Modeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 10. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with highly-embedding-connected SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 11. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 12. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with highly-multiple-connected-style SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 13. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 14. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 15. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with Linearly-Connected SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 17. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a Linearly-over-packed SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

- On the Figure (16), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 305
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- On the Figure (17), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 307
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- On the Figure (18), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 309
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- On the Figure (19), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 311
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- On the Figure (20), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 313
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- On the Figure (21), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 315
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- On the Figure (22), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 317
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Definition 3.7 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [1], Definition 2.7, p.3). 319
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Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) E_i ' and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items. 321
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(i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**; 325

(ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**; 326

Figure 18. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 19. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 20. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 21. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Definition 3.10. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0\}.$$

Definition 3.11. (General Forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)).

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where

- (i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ;
- (ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ;
- (iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'})) : T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (vii) $\sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (viii) $\sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$).

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_{V'}(E_{i'})$, $I'_{V'}(E_{i'})$, and $F'_{V'}(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the i 'th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Definition 3.12 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [1], Definition 2.7, p.3).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**;
- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**;
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**;
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**;
- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**;

(vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**.

This SuperHyperModel is too messy and too dense. Thus there's a need to have some restrictions and conditions on SuperHyperGraph. The special case of this SuperHyperGraph makes the patterns and regularities.

Definition 3.13. A graph is **SuperHyperUniform** if it's SuperHyperGraph and the number of elements of SuperHyperEdges are the same.

To get more visions on SuperHyperUniform, the some SuperHyperClasses are introduced. It makes to have SuperHyperUniform more understandable.

Definition 3.14. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some SuperHyperClasses as follows.

- (i). It's **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions;
- (ii). it's **SuperHyperCycle** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges;
- (iii). it's **SuperHyperStar** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid all SuperHyperEdges;
- (iv). it's **SuperHyperBipartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming two separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common;
- (v). it's **SuperHyperMultiPartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming multi separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common;
- (vi). it's **SuperHyperWheel** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and one SuperVertex has one SuperHyperEdge with any common SuperVertex.

Example 3.15. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the notion.

Example 3.16. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is up.

Example 3.17. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is up.

Example 3.18. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is up.

Figure 23. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath Associated to the Notions in the Example (3.15)

Figure 24. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (3.16)

Figure 25. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (3.17)

Figure 26. Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Example (3.18)

SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s$$

is called a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s if either of following conditions hold:

- (i) $V_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (ii) there's a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ such that $v_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (iii) there's a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ such that $V'_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (iv) there's a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (v) there's a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (vi) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (vii) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (viii) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (ix) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$.

Definition 3.22. (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If for all $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| = 1, |E_{j'}| = 2$, then NSHP is called **path**;
- (ii) if for all $E_{j'}, |E_{j'}| = 2$, and there's $V_i, |V_i| \geq 1$, then NSHP is called **SuperPath**;
- (iii) if for all $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| = 1, |E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **HyperPath**;
- (iv) if there are $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| \geq 1, |E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath**.

Definition 3.23 (Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths).

(Ref. [1], Definition 5.3, p.7).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

have

- (i) **Neutrosophic t-strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, m, n)_{i=1}^s$;
- (ii) **Neutrosophic i-strength** $(m, \min\{I(V_i)\}, n)_{i=1}^s$;

Table 1. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.27)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

(iii) **Neutrosophic f-strength** $(m, n, \min\{F(V_i)\}_{i=1}^s$; 459

(iv) **Neutrosophic strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\}_{i=1}^s$. 460

Definition 3.24 (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)). (Ref. [1], Definition 5.4, p.7). 461

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called 463

(ix) **Neutrosophic t-connective** if $T(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic t-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 465

(x) **Neutrosophic i-connective** if $I(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic i-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 468

(xi) **Neutrosophic f-connective** if $F(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic f-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 471

(xii) **Neutrosophic connective** if $(T(E), I(E), F(E)) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$. 474

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic notion, there's a need to "redefine" the notion of "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values. 478

Definition 3.25. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. It's redefined **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** if the Table (1) holds. 482

It's useful to define a "Neutrosophic" version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there's more ways to get Neutrosophic type-results to make a Neutrosophic more understandable. 484

Definition 3.26. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. There are some **Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses** if the Table (2) holds. Thus Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath, notion, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite, and SuperHyperWheel, are **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath**, **Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle**, **Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar**, **Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite**, **Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite**, and **Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel** if the Table (2) holds. 487

Table 2. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, Mentioned in the Definition (3.26)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Table 3. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.27)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

It's useful to define a "Neutrosophic" version of a Neutrosophic notion. Since there's more ways to get type-results to make a Neutrosophic notion more Neutrosophically understandable.

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic notion, there's a need to "redefine" the Neutrosophic notion of "Neutrosophic notion". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values.

Definition 3.27. Assume a notion. It's redefined a **Neutrosophic notion** if the Table (3) holds.

Example 3.28. Referred to the Example (3.6), assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (4).
- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (5).
- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (6).
- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (7).

Table 4. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0, 0, 0)
V_2	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_2	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)
V_3	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
V_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)

Table 5. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0, 0, 0)
V_2	(0.03, 0.03, 0.03)	E_2	(0, 0, 0)
V_3	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
V_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)

Table 6. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0, 0, 0)
V_2	(0.11, 0.11, 0.11)	E_2	(0, 0, 0)
V_3	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
-	-	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)

Table 7. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0.08, 0.08, 0.08)
V_2	(0.11, 0.11, 0.11)	E_2	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)
V_3	(0.05, 0.05, 0.05)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
V_4	(0.12, 0.12, 0.12)	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)
$\{F\}$	(0.06, 0.06, 0.06)	E_5	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)
$\{H\}$	(0.08, 0.08, 0.08)	-	-
$\{N\}$	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	-	-
$\{O\}$	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)	-	-

Figure 29. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Table 8. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyper-Edges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	$(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)$	E_1	$(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)$
V_2	$(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)$	-	-
V_3	$(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)$	-	-
V_4	$(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)$	V_5	$(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)$
V_6	$(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)$	V_7	$(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)$

4 Main Resultant

Definition 4.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_s\}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{E_i \in A_s} T(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in A_s} I(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in A_s} F(E_i))| \\
 & = \max_{B_s \subseteq E_{NSHG}} \{(\sum_{E_i \in B_s} T(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in B_s} I(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in B_s} F(E_i)) | \\
 & \quad \forall E_i, E_j, E_k \in B_s : \\
 & \quad V_a \in E_i, E_j \ \& \ V_b \in E_j, E_k \not\Rightarrow V_c \in E_i, E_k \\
 & \quad \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Example 4.2. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (29), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (8).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $E_s' = \{\}$.

Figure 30. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 31. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 32. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 33. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 34. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 35. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 36. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 37. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 38. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 39. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 40. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 41. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 42. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Table 9. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	-	-
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	-	-
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Then E_s' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & | \left(\sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{}} T(E_i), \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{}} I(E_i), \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{}} F(E_i) \right) | \\
 & = (0, 0, 0) = \\
 & \max_{E_s' \subseteq E_{NSHG}} | \left\{ \left(\sum_{E_i \in E_s''} T(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in E_s''} I(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in E_s''} F(E_i) \right) \mid \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \forall E_i, E_j, E_k \subseteq E_s' : \right. \\
 & \quad \left. V_a \in E_i, E_j \& \tilde{V}_b \in E_j, E_k \not\cong V_c \in E_i, E_k \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \right\} |.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (30), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (9).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $E_s' = \{ \}$.

Then E_s' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free

Table 10. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	-	-
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	-	-
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

search Edge criteria holds.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{}} T(E_i), \\
 & \sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{}} I(E_i), \\
 & \sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{}} F(E_i))| \\
 & = (0, 0, 0) = \\
 & \max_{E_s'' \subseteq E_{NSHG}} \{(\sum_{E_i \in E_s''} T(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in E_s''} I(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in E_s''} F(E_i)) | \\
 & \forall E_i, E_j, E_k \subseteq E_s'' : \\
 & V_a \in E_i, E_j \& V_b \in E_j, E_k \not\& V_c \in E_i, E_k \\
 & \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (31), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (10).

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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume

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SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $E_s' = \{}$.

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Then E_s' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free

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search Edge criteria holds.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{}} T(E_i), \\
 & \sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{}} I(E_i), \\
 & \sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{}} F(E_i))| \\
 & = (0, 0, 0) = \\
 & \max_{E_s'' \subseteq E_{NSHG}} \{(\sum_{E_i \in E_s''} T(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in E_s''} I(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in E_s''} F(E_i)) | \\
 & \forall E_i, E_j, E_k \subseteq E_s'' : \\
 & V_a \in E_i, E_j \& V_b \in E_j, E_k \not\& V_c \in E_i, E_k \\
 & \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (32), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (11).

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Table 11. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	-	-
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	-	-
V_4	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Table 12. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	-	-
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	-	-
V_4	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_5	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $E_s' = \{\}$. Then E_s' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{\}} T(E_i), \\
 & \sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{\}} I(E_i), \\
 & \sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{\}} F(E_i))| \\
 & = (0, 0, 0) = \\
 & \max_{E_s' \subseteq E_{NSHG}} \{(\sum_{E_i \in E_s''} T(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in E_s''} I(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in E_s''} F(E_i)) | \\
 & \forall E_i, E_j, E_k \subseteq E_s'' : \\
 & V_a \in E_i, E_j \tilde{\&} V_b \in E_j, E_k \not\tilde{\&} V_c \in E_i, E_k \\
 & \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (33), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (12).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $E_s' = \{\}$. Then E_s' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge criteria holds.

$$|(\sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{\}} T(E_i),$$

Table 13. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	-	-
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	-	-
V_4	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_5	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{}} I(E_i), \\
 & \sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{}} F(E_i) | \\
 & = (0, 0, 0) = \\
 & \max_{E_s', \subseteq E_{NSHG}} \{ (\sum_{E_i \in E_s''} T(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in E_s''} I(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in E_s''} F(E_i)) | \\
 & \forall E_i, E_j, E_k \subseteq E_s' : \\
 & V_a \in E_i, E_j \& \tilde{V}_b \in E_j, E_k \not\Rightarrow V_c \in E_i, E_k \\
 & \} |.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (34), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (13). 559
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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $E_s' = \{}$. Then E_s' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge criteria holds. 561
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$$\begin{aligned}
 & | (\sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{}} T(E_i), \\
 & \sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{}} I(E_i), \\
 & \sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{}} F(E_i)) | \\
 & = (0, 0, 0) = \\
 & \max_{E_s', \subseteq E_{NSHG}} \{ (\sum_{E_i \in E_s''} T(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in E_s''} I(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in E_s''} F(E_i)) | \\
 & \forall E_i, E_j, E_k \subseteq E_s' : \\
 & V_a \in E_i, E_j \& \tilde{V}_b \in E_j, E_k \not\Rightarrow V_c \in E_i, E_k \\
 & \} |.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (35), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (14). 566
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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $E_s' = \{}$. 568
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Table 14. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	-	-
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	-	-
V_4	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_5	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)

Table 15. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=37}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Then E_s' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & | \left(\sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{ \}} T(E_i), \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{ \}} I(E_i), \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{ \}} F(E_i) \right) | \\
 & = (0, 0, 0) = \\
 & \max_{E_s'' \subseteq E_{NSHG}} \left\{ \left(\sum_{E_i \in E_s''} T(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in E_s''} I(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in E_s''} F(E_i) \right) \mid \right. \\
 & \quad \forall E_i, E_j, E_k \subseteq E_s'' : \\
 & \quad \left. V_a \in E_i, E_j \& V_b \in E_j, E_k \not\Rightarrow V_c \in E_i, E_k \right\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Example 4.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (36), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (15).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $E_s' = \{E_i\}_{i=1-3}$. Then E_s' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge criteria holds.

$$\left| \left(\sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{E_i\}_{i=1-3}} T(E_i), \right. \right.$$

Table 16. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=37}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{E_i\}_{i=1-3}} I(E_i), \\
 & \sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{E_i\}_{i=1-3}} F(E_i) | \\
 & = (0.78, 0.78, 0.78) = \\
 & \max_{E_s' \subseteq E_{NSHG}} \{ (\sum_{E_i \in E_s''} T(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in E_s''} I(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in E_s''} F(E_i)) | \\
 & \forall E_i, E_j, E_k \subseteq E_s' : \\
 & V_a \in E_i, E_j \tilde{\&} V_b \in E_j, E_k \not\tilde{\&} V_c \in E_i, E_k \\
 & \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (37), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (16). 582
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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $E_s' = \{E_i\}_{i=1-3}$. Then E_s' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge criteria holds. 584
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$$\begin{aligned}
 & | (\sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{E_i\}_{i=1-3}} T(E_i), \\
 & \sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{E_i\}_{i=1-3}} I(E_i), \\
 & \sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{E_i\}_{i=1-3}} F(E_i) | \\
 & = (0.78, 0.78, 0.78) = \\
 & \max_{E_s' \subseteq E_{NSHG}} \{ (\sum_{E_i \in E_s''} T(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in E_s''} I(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in E_s''} F(E_i)) | \\
 & \forall E_i, E_j, E_k \subseteq E_s' : \\
 & V_a \in E_i, E_j \tilde{\&} V_b \in E_j, E_k \not\tilde{\&} V_c \in E_i, E_k \\
 & \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (38), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (17). 589
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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $E_s' = \{E_i\}_{i=1-3}$. Then E_s' is called Neutrosophic 591
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Table 17. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=3^7}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Table 18. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=3^7}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & | \left(\sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{E_i\}_{i=1-3}} T(E_i), \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{E_i\}_{i=1-3}} I(E_i), \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{E_i\}_{i=1-3}} F(E_i) \right) | \\
 & = (0.78, 0.78, 0.78) = \\
 & \max_{E_s'' \subseteq E_{NSHG}} \left\{ \left(\sum_{E_i \in E_s''} T(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in E_s''} I(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in E_s''} F(E_i) \right) \mid \right. \\
 & \quad \forall E_i, E_j, E_k \subseteq E_s'' : \\
 & \quad \left. V_a \in E_i, E_j \& V_b \in E_j, E_k \not\& V_c \in E_i, E_k \right\} |.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (39), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (18).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $E_s' = \{E_i\}_{i=1-3}$. Then E_s' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & | \left(\sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{E_i\}_{i=1-3}} T(E_i), \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{E_i\}_{i=1-3}} I(E_i), \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{E_i\}_{i=1-3}} F(E_i) \right) |
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 19. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=3}^7$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= (0.78, 0.78, 0.78) = \\
 &\max_{E_s' \subseteq E_{NSHG}} \left\{ \left(\sum_{E_i \in E_s'} T(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in E_s'} I(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in E_s'} F(E_i) \right) \mid \right. \\
 &\quad \forall E_i, E_j, E_k \subseteq E_s' : \\
 &\quad \left. V_a \in E_i, E_j \&\tilde{V}_b \in E_j, E_k \not\& V_c \in E_i, E_k \right\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (40), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (19).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $E_s' = \{E_i\}_{i=1-3}$. Then E_s' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left| \left(\sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{E_i\}_{i=1-3}} T(E_i), \right. \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{E_i\}_{i=1-3}} I(E_i), \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{E_i\}_{i=1-3}} F(E_i) \right| \\
 &= (0.78, 0.78, 0.78) = \\
 &\max_{E_s' \subseteq E_{NSHG}} \left\{ \left(\sum_{E_i \in E_s'} T(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in E_s'} I(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in E_s'} F(E_i) \right) \mid \right. \\
 &\quad \forall E_i, E_j, E_k \subseteq E_s' : \\
 &\quad \left. V_a \in E_i, E_j \&\tilde{V}_b \in E_j, E_k \not\& V_c \in E_i, E_k \right\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (41), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (20).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $E_s' = \{E_i\}_{i=1-3}$. Then E_s' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge criteria holds.

$$\left| \left(\sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{E_i\}_{i=1-3}} T(E_i), \right. \right.$$

Table 20. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=3^7}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Table 21. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=3^7}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{E_i\}_{i=1-3}} I(E_i), \\
 & \sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{E_i\}_{i=1-3}} F(E_i) \\
 & = (0.78, 0.78, 0.78) = \\
 & \max_{E_s'' \subseteq E_{NSHG}} \left\{ \left(\sum_{E_i \in E_s''} T(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in E_s''} I(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in E_s''} F(E_i) \right) \mid \right. \\
 & \quad \forall E_i, E_j, E_k \subseteq E_s'' : \\
 & \quad V_a \in E_i, E_j \& \tilde{V}_b \in E_j, E_k \not\approx V_c \in E_i, E_k \\
 & \left. \right\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (42), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (21).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $E_s' = \{E_i\}_{i=1-3}$. Then E_s' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \left(\sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{E_i\}_{i=1-3}} T(E_i), \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{E_i\}_{i=1-3}} I(E_i), \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \sum_{E_i \in E_s' = \{E_i\}_{i=1-3}} F(E_i) \right) \right| \\
 & = (0.78, 0.78, 0.78) = \\
 & \max_{E_s'' \subseteq E_{NSHG}} \left\{ \left(\sum_{E_i \in E_s''} T(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in E_s''} I(E_i), \sum_{E_i \in E_s''} F(E_i) \right) \mid \right. \\
 & \quad \forall E_i, E_j, E_k \subseteq E_s'' :
 \end{aligned}$$

$$V_a \in E_i, E_j \& \tilde{V}_b \in E_j, E_k \not\neq V_c \in E_i, E_k \} |.$$

5 Main Result

Theorem 5.1. (Main Result and Main Theorem).

Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite has the letter z . The notion on the Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite and Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath coincide.

Proof.

(i). Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_1}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_1}, E_2$$

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_1}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_1}, E_2$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge. The latter is straightforward.

(ii). Let

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

is a longest SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHC : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free

search Edge. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. □

Proposition 5.2. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite ESHM be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge set is as follows.*

$$\{V^{P_1}\}.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_1}, E_1, \\ V_2^{P_1}, E_2$$

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_1}, E_1, \\ V_2^{P_1}, E_2$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge. The latter is straightforward. □

Proposition 5.3. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite ESHM be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge number is as follows.*

$$|V^{P_1}| \times 0.26.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_1}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_1}, E_2$$

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv$$

$$\begin{aligned} \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.4. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (ESHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge set is as follows.*

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} V_i^{EXTERNAL}, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, \dots \end{array} \right\}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \begin{array}{l} V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^* \end{array}$$

$$P : \begin{array}{l} V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^* \end{array}$$

is a longest SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHG : (V, E)$. There’s a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge. The latter is straightforward. Then there’s at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge. Thus the notion of quasi isn’t up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.5. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (ESHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge number is as follows.*

$$\frac{|V|}{2} \times 0.26.$$

Proof. Let

$$P :$$

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

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$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

is a longest SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Definition 5.6. (Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite and Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath).

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(i). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Every pair of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices has the same maximum letter, i.e., Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices mutually has the same maximum letter. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$ is called **Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite**.

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(ii). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Every pair of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices has the same maximum letter, i.e., Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices mutually has the same maximum letter. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$ is called **Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath**.

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Proposition 5.7. Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHM$ be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge set is as follows.

$$\{V^{P_1}\}.$$

Proof. Let

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$$P : \\ V_1^{P_1}, E_1, \\ V_2^{P_1}, E_2$$

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$$P : \\ V_1^{P_1}, E_1, \\ V_2^{P_1}, E_2$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyper^{Triangle-free} search Edge. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.8. *Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHM$ be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyper^{Triangle-free} search Edge number is as follows.*

$$|V^{P_1}| \times 0.26.$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{P_1}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_1}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{P_1}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_1}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyper^{Triangle-free} search Edge. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.9. *Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath ($ESHC$) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyper^{Triangle-free} search Edge set is as follows.*

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} &V_i^{EXTERNAL}, \\ &V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, \dots \end{aligned} \right\}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^* \end{aligned}$$

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

is a longest SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHC : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.10. *Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (ESHC) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge number is as follows.*

$$\frac{|V|}{2} \times 0.26.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

is a longest SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHC : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.11. (*Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite and Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath*).

- (i). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume two Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, from different SuperHyperParts, have the maximum letter. Then the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices don't have the same maximum letter, are in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge set.
- (ii). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic EXTERNAL SuperHyperVertices with distance two have the maximum letter. Then the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices don't have the same maximum letter, are in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge set.

Proof.

(i). Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge. The latter is straightforward.

(ii). Let

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

is a longest SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHC : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv$$

$$\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge. The latter is straightforward. Then there’s at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge. Thus the notion of quasi isn’t up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. □

Proposition 5.12. (*Embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite and Embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath*).

- (i). *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG) S be a pair S = (V, E). Then two Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, from different SuperHyperParts, is in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge set.*
- (ii). *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG) S be a pair S = (V, E). Then every Neutrosophic EXTERNAL SuperHyperVertices with distance two is in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge set.*

Proof.

- (i). Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There’s a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge. The latter is straightforward.

- (ii). Let

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

$$P :$$

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

is a longest SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. □

6 Neutrosophic Applications in Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition

The cancer is the Neutrosophic disease but the Neutrosophic model is going to figure out what's going on this Neutrosophic phenomenon. The special Neutrosophic case of this Neutrosophic disease is considered and as the consequences of the model, some parameters are used. The cells are under attack of this disease but the moves of the cancer in the special region are the matter of mind. The Neutrosophic recognition of the cancer could help to find some Neutrosophic treatments for this Neutrosophic disease.

In the following, some Neutrosophic steps are Neutrosophic devised on this disease.

Step 1. (Neutrosophic Definition) The Neutrosophic recognition of the cancer in the long-term Neutrosophic function.

Step 2. (Neutrosophic Issue) The specific region has been assigned by the Neutrosophic model [it's called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] and the long Neutrosophic cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn't be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it's said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what's happened and what's done.

Step 3. (Neutrosophic Model) There are some specific Neutrosophic models, which are well-known and they've got the names, and some general Neutrosophic models. The moves and the Neutrosophic traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge or the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge in those Neutrosophic Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels.

Figure 43. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Associated to the Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge

Table 22. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

7 Case 1: The Initial Neutrosophic Steps Toward Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite as Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel

Step 4. (Neutrosophic Solution) In the Neutrosophic Figure (43), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured.
 By using the Neutrosophic Figure (43) and the Table (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite is obtained.
 The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (43), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge.

Figure 44. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Associated to the Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge

Table 23. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

8 Case 2: The Increasing Neutrosophic Steps Toward Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite as Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel

Step 4. (Neutrosophic Solution) In the Neutrosophic Figure (44), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. By using the Neutrosophic Figure (44) and the Table (23), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite is obtained. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (44), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge.

9 Wondering Open Problems But As The Directions To Forming The Motivations

In what follows, some “problems” and some “questions” are proposed. The SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge are defined on a real-world application, titled “Cancer’s Recognitions”.

Question 9.1. Which the else SuperHyperModels could be defined based on Cancer’s

recognitions?

Question 9.2. *Are there some SuperHyperNotions related to SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge?*

Question 9.3. *Are there some Algorithms to be defined on the SuperHyperModels to compute them?*

Question 9.4. *Which the SuperHyperNotions are related to beyond the SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge?*

Problem 9.5. *The SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge do a SuperHyperModel for the Cancer's recognitions and they're based on SuperHyperTriangle-free search Edge, are there else?*

Problem 9.6. *Which the fundamental SuperHyperNumbers are related to these SuperHyperNumbers types-results?*

Problem 9.7. *What's the independent research based on Cancer's recognitions concerning the multiple types of SuperHyperNotions?*

10 Conclusion and Closing Remarks

In this section, closing and concluding remarks are presented. The drawbacks of this scientific research are shown. Some advantages and disadvantages of this scientific research are highlighted.

This scientific research uses some approaches to further understand the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs. In this effort, two SuperHyperNotions are defined on the Triangle-free search Edge. For this reason, in the second definition, the original definition of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph is redefined on the position of the alphabets. Based on the new Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph definition, the new SuperHyperNotion, Neutrosophic Triangle-free search Edge, finds a suitable background to implement some results on. Some SuperHyperClasses and some Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses are the subjects of this scientific research on modeling areas that are subject to cancer attacks in order to recognize this disease as mentioned under the title "Cancer Diagnosis". To formalize the SuperHyperNotion, Triangle-free search Edge, SuperHyperClasses and new SuperHyperClasses instances are introduced. Some general results are summarized in the Triangle-free search Edge and Neutrosophic Triangle-free search Edge sections. Clarifications, examples, and literature reviews go all the way. In this scientific research, the literature review has met the lines containing concepts and results. SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are super-hypermodels in "cancer diagnosis" and both are the foundation of the background of this scientific research. Sometimes cancer has occurred in an area full of cells, cell groups, and embedded styles. In this section, SuperHyperModel proposes SuperHyperNotions, formally called "Triangle-free search Edge", based on the connections of Cancer's movements in the longest and strongest styles with the formation of design and architecture, in terms of terms and whispering words. . The "SuperHyper" prefix refers to the topic of embedded styles to explore the background of SuperHyperNotions. In the table (24), the advantages and ways of this scientific research are specified, pointed out and expressed.

11 Background

There are some scientific researches covering the topic of this scientific research. In what follows, there are some discussion and literature reviews about them.

Table 24. A look at this scientific research and beyond

Advantages	Limitations
1. Redefining the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph	1. General Results
2. Triangle-free search Edge	
3. Neutrosophic Triangle-free search Edge	2. Other SuperHyperNumbers
4. modeling cancer diagnoses	
5. SuperHyperClasses	3. SuperHyperFamilies

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph As Hyper Tool On Super Toot*” in **Ref. [1]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on general forms with introducing used neutrosophic classes of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*Current Trends in Mass Communication (CTMC)*” with ISO abbreviation “*Curr Trends Mass Comm*” in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 32-55.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*” in **Ref. [2]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental notions and using vital tools in Cancer’s Treatments. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*” with ISO abbreviation “*J Math Techniques Comput Math*” in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 35-47. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*A Research on Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic Super Hypergraph by Eulerian Super Hyper Cycles and Hamiltonian Sets as Hyper Covering Versus Super separations*” in **Ref. [3]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental notions and using vital tools in Cancer’s Recognition. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*” with ISO abbreviation “*J Math Techniques Comput Math*” in volume 2 and issue 3 with pages 136-148. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction to Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Beyond*” in **Ref. [4]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*” with ISO abbreviation “*J Math Techniques Comput Math*” in volume 2 and issue 6 with pages 221-307. The research article studies

deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph by Initial Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Initial Eulogy on Super Initial EULA" in **Ref. [5]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research" with ISO abbreviation "IJPAMR" in volume 3 and issue 2 with pages 60-88 and doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.60-88. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graph by Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut on Super EULA-Path-Cut" in **Ref. [6]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research" with ISO abbreviation "IJPAMR" in volume 3 and issue 2 with pages 102-124 and doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.102-124. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "Super Hyper Dominating and Super Hyper Resolving on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs and Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Classes" in **Ref. [7]** by Henry Garrett (2022). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)" with ISO abbreviation "J Math Techniques Comput Math" in volume 1 and issue 3 with pages 242-263. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "neutrosophic co-degree and neutrosophic degree alongside chromatic numbers in the setting of some classes related to neutrosophic hypergraphs" in **Ref. [8]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on general forms without using neutrosophic classes of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "Journal of Current Trends in Computer Science Research (JCTCSR)" with ISO abbreviation "J Curr Trends Comp Sci Res" in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 16-24. The research article studies deeply with choosing neutrosophic hypergraphs instead of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background. The research article studies deeply with choosing neutrosophic hypergraphs instead of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background. In some articles are titled "0039 — Closing Numbers and Super-Closing Numbers as (Dual)Resolving and (Dual)Coloring alongside (Dual)Dominating in (Neutrosophic)n-SuperHyperGraph" in **Ref. [9]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "0049 — (Failed)1-Zero-Forcing Number in Neutrosophic Graphs" in **Ref. [10]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer's Recognition as the Model in The Setting of

(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [11]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition*” in **Ref. [12]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [13]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*” in **Ref. [14]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [15]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [16]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [17]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [18]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*” in **Ref. [19]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*” in **Ref. [20]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [21]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*” in **Ref. [17]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [22]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*” in **Ref. [23]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances*” in **Ref. [24]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses*” in **Ref. [25]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions*” in **Ref. [26]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*” in **Ref. [27]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses*” in **Ref. [28]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*SuperHyperMatching By (R-)Definitions And Polynomials To Monitor Cancer’s Recognition In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [276]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “*The Focus on The Partitions Obtained By Parallel Moves In The Cancer’s Extreme Recognition With Different Types of Extreme SuperHyperMatching Set and Polynomial on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [277]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer’s Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer’s Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [278]** by Henry Garrett (2023),

“Indeterminacy On The All Possible Connections of Cells In Front of Cancer’s Attacks In The Terms of Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique on Cancer’s Recognition called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [279]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Perfect Directions Toward Idealism in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Forwarding Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [282]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Demonstrating Complete Connections in Every Embedded Regions and Sub-Regions in the Terms of Cancer’s Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClique” in **Ref. [283]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic Regions titled neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition modeled in the Form of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [286]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Using the Tool As (Neutrosophic) Failed SuperHyperStable To SuperHyperModel Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [289]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [290]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well-SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [291]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond” in **Ref. [292]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [293]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [294]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Basic Neutrosophic Notions Concerning SuperHyperDominating and Neutrosophic SuperHyperResolving in SuperHyperGraph” in **Ref. [305]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Initial Material of Neutrosophic Preliminaries to Study Some Neutrosophic Notions Based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)” in **Ref. [306]** by Henry Garrett (2022), and [4–306], there are some endeavors to formalize the basic SuperHyperNotions about neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph alongside scientific research books at [307–459]. Two popular scientific research books in Scribd in the terms of high readers, 5679 and 6667 respectively, on neutrosophic science is on [460, 461].

Some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [460]** by Henry Garrett (2023) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 5679 readers in Scribd. It’s titled “Beyond Neutrosophic Graphs” and published by Dr. Henry Garrett. This research book covers different types of notions and settings in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory.

Also, some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [461]** by Henry Garrett (2023) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 6667 readers in Scribd. It’s titled “Neutrosophic Duality” and published by Dr. Henry Garrett. This research book presents different types of notions SuperHyperResolving and SuperHyperDominating in the setting of duality in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory. This research book has scrutiny on the complement of the intended set and the intended set, simultaneously. It’s smart to consider a set but acting on its complement that what’s done in this research book which is popular in the terms of high readers in Scribd.

See the seminal scientific researches [1–3]. The formalization of the notions on the framework of notions in SuperHyperGraphs, Neutrosophic notions in SuperHyperGraphs theory, and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs theory at [4–306] alongside scientific research books at [307–459]. Two popular scientific research books in Scribd ,in the terms of high readers, 5679 and 6667 respectively, on neutrosophic

science is on [460, 461].

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References

1102

1. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph As Hyper Tool On Super Toot”, *Curr Trends Mass Comm* 2(1) (2023) 32-55. (doi: 10.33140/CTMC.02.01.03). 1103
1104
1105
2. Henry Garrett, “Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments”, *J Math Techniques Comput Math* 2(1) (2023) 35-47. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.02.01.05). 1106
1107
1108
1109
3. Henry Garrett, “A Research on Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic Super Hypergraph by Eulerian Super Hyper Cycles and Hamiltonian Sets as Hyper Covering Versus Super separations”, *J Math Techniques Comput Math* 2(3) (2023) 136-148. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.02.03.03). 1110
1111
1112
1113
4. Henry Garrett, “Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction to Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Beyond”, *J Math Techniques Comput Math* 2(6) (2023) 221-307. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.02.06.04). 1114
1115
1116
1117
5. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph by Initial Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Initial Eulogy on Super Initial EULA”, *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research* 3(2) (2023) 60-88. (doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.60-88). 1118
1119
1120
1121
6. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graph by Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut on Super EULA-Path-Cut”, *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research* 3(2) (2023) 102-124. (doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.102-124). 1122
1123
1124
1125
7. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graph by Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut on Super EULA-Path-Cut”, *J Curr Trends Comp Sci Res* 2(1) (2023) 16-24. (doi: 10.33140/JCTCSR.02.01.04) 1126
1127
1128
1129
8. Henry Garrett, “Super Hyper Dominating and Super Hyper Resolving on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs and Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Classes”, *J Math Techniques Comput Math* 1(3) (2022) 242-263. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.01.03.09) 1130
1131
1132
1133
9. Garrett, Henry. “0039 — Closing Numbers and Super-Closing Numbers as (Dual)Resolving and (Dual)Coloring alongside (Dual)Dominating in (Neutrosophic)n-SuperHyperGraph.” CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research - Zenodo, Nov. 2022. CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6319942>. <https://oa.mg/work/10.5281/zenodo.6319942> 1134
1135
1136
1137
1138
1139
10. Garrett, Henry. “0049 — (Failed)1-Zero-Forcing Number in Neutrosophic Graphs.” CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research - Zenodo, Feb. 2022. CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research, <https://doi.org/10.13140/rg.2.2.35241.26724>. <https://oa.mg/work/10.13140/rg.2.2.35241.26724> 1140
1141
1142
1143
1144

11. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010308 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0308.v1). 1145
1146
1147
1148
12. Henry Garrett, “*Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010282 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0282.v1). 1149
1150
1151
1152
13. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010267 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0267.v1). 1153
1154
1155
14. Henry Garrett, “*The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010265 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0265.v1). 1156
1157
1158
1159
1160
1161
15. Henry Garrett, “*Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010262,(doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0262.v1). 1162
1163
1164
1165
16. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010240 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0240.v1). 1166
1167
1168
1169
17. Henry Garrett, “*Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010224, (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0224.v1). 1170
1171
1172
1173
18. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 1174
1175
1176
19. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1). 1177
1178
1179
1180
20. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010044 1181
1182
1183
21. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010043 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0043.v1). 1184
1185
1186
22. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 1187
1188
1189
1190

23. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1). 1191
1192
1193
1194
24. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120549 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0549.v1). 1195
1196
1197
25. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120540 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0540.v1). 1198
1199
1200
1201
1202
26. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120500 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0500.v1). 1203
1204
1205
27. Henry Garrett, “*Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120324 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0324.v1). 1206
1207
1208
1209
28. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses*”, Preprints 2022, 2022110576 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202211.0576.v1). 1210
1211
1212
1213
29. Henry Garrett, “*Star and Wheel on Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph with a Specific Type of Independency of SuperHyperVertices*”, Preprints 2024, , 2024020663 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202402.0663.v1). 1214
1215
1216
1217
30. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Diamond search*”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13834065). 1218
1219
1220
31. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Diamond search*”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13826744). 1221
1222
1223
32. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Diamond search*”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13823150). 1224
1225
1226
33. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Triangle-free search*”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13748678). 1227
1228
1229
34. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Triangle-free search*”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13629264). 1230
1231
1232
35. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Triangle-free search*”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13618512). 1233
1234
1235

36. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Edge Cover", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13457634). 1236
1237
1238
37. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Edge Cover", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13447621). 1239
1240
1241
38. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Edge Cover", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13386125). 1242
1243
1244
39. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Vertex Cover", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13359880). 1245
1246
1247
40. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Vertex Cover", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13359103). 1248
1249
1250
41. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Vertex Cover", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13329472). 1251
1252
1253
42. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Burning Number From Graph Searching", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13091499). 1254
1255
1256
43. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Burning Number From Graph Searching", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13134329). 1257
1258
1259
44. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Burning Number From Graph Searching", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13218489). 1260
1261
1262
45. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Zero Forcing From Graph Searching", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12788786). 1263
1264
1265
46. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Zero Forcing", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12752339). 1266
1267
1268
47. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Zero Forcing", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12738172). 1269
1270
1271
48. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Connected Perfect Dual Domination", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12680424). 1272
1273
1274
49. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Connected Perfect Dual Domination", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12675758). 1275
1276
1277
50. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Connected Perfect Dual Domination", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12656919). 1278
1279
1280

51. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Stable Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12576337). 1281
1282
1283
52. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Stable Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12556338). 1284
1285
1286
53. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Stable Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12536399). 1287
1288
1289
54. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12174846). 1290
1291
1292
55. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12129978). 1293
1294
1295
56. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12024191). 1296
1297
1298
57. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Connected Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11661528). 1299
1300
1301
58. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Connected Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11651866). 1302
1303
1304
59. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Connected Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11634496). 1305
1306
1307
60. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Stable Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11513482). 1308
1309
1310
61. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Stable Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11479559). 1311
1312
1313
62. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Stable Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11438586). 1314
1315
1316
63. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Simple Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11253553). 1317
1318
1319
64. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Simple Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11218489). 1320
1321
1322
65. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Simple Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11169069). 1323
1324
1325

66. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Stable Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11075522). 1326
1327
1328
67. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Stable Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10982844). 1329
1330
1331
68. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Stable Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10963312). 1332
1333
1334
69. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Total Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10929590). 1335
1336
1337
70. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Total Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10918770). 1338
1339
1340
71. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Total Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10910154). 1341
1342
1343
72. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10899659). 1344
1345
1346
73. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10895887). 1347
1348
1349
74. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10888691). 1350
1351
1352
75. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Counterproposal Star and Counteroffer Wheel By Counterargument Stable Sequence As Hyper Findings On Super Gatherings”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10851065). 1353
1354
1355
1356
76. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Counterproposal Bipartite and Counteroffer Path By Counterargument Stable Sequence As Hyper Findings On Super Gatherings”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10796076). 1357
1358
1359
1360
77. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Counterproposal Multipartite and Counteroffer Cycle By Counterargument Stable Sequence As Hyper Findings On Super Gatherings”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10640905). 1361
1362
1363
1364
78. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Strongly Resolving Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17389.97769). 1365
1366
1367
1368

79. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Strongly Resolving Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28685.10727). 1369
1370
1371
1372
80. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Strongly Resolving Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.24994.20169). 1373
1374
1375
1376
81. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Dominating Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10371529). 1377
1378
1379
82. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Dominating Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10299535). 1380
1381
1382
83. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Dominating Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10263440). 1383
1384
1385
1386
84. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By STABLE As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10028600). 1387
1388
1389
85. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By STABLE As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8310454). 1390
1391
1392
86. Henry Garrett, “Recognition of Cancer With Bipartite and Path as Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By the Tool Called Stability”, Preprints 2023, 2023081972 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202308.1972.v1). 1393
1394
1395
87. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By STABLE As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8262182). 1396
1397
1398
88. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By REVERSE CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206877). 1399
1400
1401
1402
89. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By REVERSE CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206834). 1403
1404
1405
1406
90. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By REVERSE CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206773). 1407
1408
1409
1410
91. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By EQUAL CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201319). 1411
1412
1413
1414

92. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By EQUAL CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201255). 1415
1416
1417
1418
93. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By EQUAL CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201165). 1419
1420
1421
1422
94. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8196147). 1423
1424
1425
1426
95. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8196132). 1427
1428
1429
1430
96. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8196099). 1431
1432
1433
1434
97. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8187955). 1435
1436
1437
98. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8161878). 1438
1439
1440
99. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8176262). 1441
1442
1443
100. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperPerfect Search As Hyper Perf On Super Perfidy”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8104836). 1444
1445
1446
101. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Perfidy By Hyper Perf Of SuperHyperPerfect Search In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8104857). 1447
1448
1449
102. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Strict Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8092796). 1450
1451
1452
103. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Reverse Strict Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8092766). 1453
1454
1455
104. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Unequal Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8088438). 1456
1457
1458

105. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Unequal Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8088387). 1459
1460
1461
106. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Strict Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8084436). 1462
1463
1464
107. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Strict Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8084420). 1465
1466
1467
108. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Strict Connective As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8080100). 1468
1469
1470
109. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Reverse Strict Connective In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8080068). 1471
1472
1473
110. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Unequal Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8078445). 1474
1475
1476
111. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Unequal Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8078543). 1477
1478
1479
112. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Strict Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8076416). 1480
1481
1482
113. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Strict Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8076399). 1483
1484
1485
114. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8072171). 1486
1487
1488
115. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Reverse Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8072267). 1489
1490
1491
116. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Equal Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8067384). 1492
1493
1494
117. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Equal Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8067409). 1495
1496
1497
118. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8061927). 1498
1499
1500
119. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8062016). 1501
1502
1503

120. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8057696). 1504
1505
1506
121. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Reverse Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8057753). 1507
1508
1509
122. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Equal Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8052893). 1510
1511
1512
123. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Equal Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8052925). 1513
1514
1515
124. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8051346). 1516
1517
1518
125. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8051360). 1519
1520
1521
126. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By United Dominating As Hyper Ultra On Super Units”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8025707). 1522
1523
1524
127. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Units By Hyper Ultra Of United Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8027275). 1525
1526
1527
128. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Zero Forcing As Hyper ford On Super forceps”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8017246). 1528
1529
1530
129. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super forceps By Hyper ford Of Zero Forcing In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8020128). 1531
1532
1533
130. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Matrix-Based As Hyper mat On Super matte”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7978571). 1534
1535
1536
131. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super mat By Hyper matte Of Matrix-Based In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7978857). 1537
1538
1539
132. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Dominating-Edges As Hyper Dome On Super Eddy”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7940830). 1540
1541
1542
133. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Eddy By Hyper Dome Of Dominating-Edges In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7943578). 1543
1544
1545
134. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Gap As Hyper Gape On Super Gab”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7916595). 1546
1547
1548

135. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Gab By Hyper Gape Of Edge-Gap In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7923632). 1549
1550
1551
136. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904698). 1552
1553
1554
137. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904671). 1555
1556
1557
138. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904529). 1558
1559
1560
1561
139. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904401). 1562
1563
1564
1565
140. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7871026). 1566
1567
1568
141. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7874647). 1569
1570
1571
142. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7857856). 1572
1573
1574
143. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Cycle-Neighbor In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7857841). 1575
1576
1577
144. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7855661). 1578
1579
1580
145. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Cycle-Decomposition In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7855637). 1581
1582
1583
146. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Eulogy On Super EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7853867). 1584
1585
1586
147. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super EULA By Hyper Eulogy Of Eulerian-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7853922). 1587
1588
1589
148. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Path-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7851519). 1590
1591
1592

149. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Type-Path-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph)*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7851550). 1593
1594
1595
150. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Path-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7839333). 1596
1597
1598
151. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Type-Path-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph)*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7840206). 1599
1600
1601
152. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Path-Cut As Hyper Eulogy On Super EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7834229). 1602
1603
1604
153. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super EULA By Hyper Eulogy Of Eulerian-Type-Path-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph)*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7834261). 1605
1606
1607
154. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7824560). 1608
1609
1610
155. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Path-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph)*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7824623). 1611
1612
1613
156. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7819531). 1614
1615
1616
157. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Path-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph)*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7819579). 1617
1618
1619
158. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph As Hyper Tool On Super Toot*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7812236). 1620
1621
1622
159. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By initial Eulerian-Path-Cut As Hyper initial Eulogy On Super initial EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809365). 1623
1624
1625
160. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Cut As Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut On Super EULA-Path-Cut*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809358). 1626
1627
1628
161. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super EULA By Hyper Eulogy Of Eulerian-Path-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph)*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809219). 1629
1630
1631
162. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Cut As Hyper Eulogy On Super EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809328). 1632
1633
1634
163. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7806767). 1635
1636
1637

164. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7806838). 1638
1639
1640
165. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804238). 1641
1642
1643
1644
166. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804228). 1645
1646
1647
167. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Hamper On Super Hammy*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7799902). 1648
1649
1650
168. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Hammy By Hyper Hamper Of Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804218). 1651
1652
1653
169. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7796334). 1654
1655
1656
170. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7793372). 1657
1658
1659
171. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Hamper On Super Hammy*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7791952). 1660
1661
1662
172. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Hammy By Hyper Hamper Of Hamiltonian-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7791982). 1663
1664
1665
173. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7790026). 1666
1667
1668
174. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Hamiltonian-Neighbor In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7790052). 1669
1670
1671
175. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7787066). 1672
1673
1674
176. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Hamiltonian-Decomposition In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7787094). 1675
1676
1677
177. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cut As Hyper Hamper On Super Hammy*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7781476). 1678
1679
1680

178. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Hammy By Hyper Hamper Of Hamiltonian-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7783082). 1681
1682
1683
179. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Trace-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7777857). 1684
1685
1686
180. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Trace-Neighbor In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7779286). 1687
1688
1689
181. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Trace-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decompensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7771831). 1690
1691
1692
182. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decompensation By Hyper Decompress Of Trace-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7772468). 1693
1694
1695
183. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Trace-Cut As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20913.25446). 1696
1697
1698
184. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Tract By Hyper Track Of Trace-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7764916). 1699
1700
1701
185. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11770.98247). 1702
1703
1704
186. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Edge-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.12400.12808). 1705
1706
1707
187. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decompensation*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.22545.10089). 1708
1709
1710
188. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decompensation By Hyper Decompress Of Edge-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29544.34564). 1711
1712
1713
189. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Cut As Hyper Edify On Super Eddy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11377.76644). 1714
1715
1716
190. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Eddy By Hyper Edify Of Edge-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23750.96329). 1717
1718
1719
191. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31366.24641). 1720
1721
1722
192. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Vertex-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34721.68960). 1723
1724
1725

193. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30212.81289). 1726
1727
1728
194. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Vertex-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18468.76169). 1729
1730
1731
195. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Cut As Hyper Vertu On Super Vertigo*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.24288.35842). 1732
1733
1734
196. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Vertigo By Hyper Vertu Of Vertex-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32467.25124). 1735
1736
1737
197. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Stable-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31025.45925). 1738
1739
1740
198. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulizer By Hyper Nub Of Stable-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17184.25602). 1741
1742
1743
199. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Stable-Decompositions As Hyper Stain On Super Stagy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23423.28327). 1744
1745
1746
200. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Stale By Hyper Stalk Of Stable-Decompositions In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28456.44805). 1747
1748
1749
201. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Stable-Cut As Hyper Stain On Super Stagy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23525.68320). 1750
1751
1752
202. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Stale By Hyper Stalk Of Stable-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20170.24000). 1753
1754
1755
203. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Clique-Neighbors As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36475.59683). 1756
1757
1758
204. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulizer By Hyper Nub Of Clique-Neighbors In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29764.71046). 1759
1760
1761
205. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Clique-Decompositions As Hyper Decompile On Super Decommission*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18780.87683). 1762
1763
1764
206. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Clique- Decompositions In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.27169.48487). 1765
1766
1767
207. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Clique-Cut As Hyper Click On Super Cliche*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26134.01603). 1768
1769
1770

208. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Cliff By Hyper Cling Of Clique-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.27392.30721). 1771
1772
1773
209. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Space As Hyper Spin On Super Spacy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33028.40321). 1774
1775
1776
210. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By List- Coloring As Hyper List On Super Lisle*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21389.20966). 1777
1778
1779
211. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Lith By Hyper Lite Of List-Coloring In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.16356.04489). 1780
1781
1782
212. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Space As Hyper Sparse On Super Spark*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21756.21129). 1783
1784
1785
213. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Solidarity By Hyper Soul Of Space In Cancer’s Recognition With (Extreme) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30983.68009). 1786
1787
1788
214. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Connectivity As Hyper Disclosure On Super Closure*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28552.29445). 1789
1790
1791
215. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Uniform By Hyper Deformation Of Edge-Connectivity In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.10936.21761). 1792
1793
1794
216. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Connectivity As Hyper Leak On Super Structure*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35105.89447). 1795
1796
1797
217. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super System By Hyper Explosions Of Vertex-Connectivity In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30072.72960). 1798
1799
1800
218. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Tree-Decomposition As Hyper Forward On Super Returns*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31147.52003). 1801
1802
1803
219. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nodes By Hyper Moves Of Tree-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32825.24163). 1804
1805
1806
220. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Chord As Hyper Excellence On Super Excess*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13059.58401). 1807
1808
1809
221. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Gap By Hyper Navigations Of Chord In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11172.14720). 1810
1811
1812
222. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyper(i,j)-Domination As Hyper Controller On Super Waves*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.22011.80165). 1813
1814
1815

223. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Coincidence By Hyper Routes Of SuperHyper(i,j)-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30819.84003). 1816
1817
1818
224. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperEdge-Domination As Hyper Reversion On Super Indirection*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.10493.84962). 1819
1820
1821
225. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Obstacles By Hyper Model Of SuperHyperEdge-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13849.29280). 1822
1823
1824
226. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperK-Domination As Hyper k-Actions On Super Patterns*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19944.14086). 1825
1826
1827
227. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Harmony By Hyper k-Function Of SuperHyperK-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23299.58404). 1828
1829
1830
228. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperK-Number As Hyper k-Partition On Super Layers*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33103.76968). 1831
1832
1833
229. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Gradient By Hyper k-Class Of SuperHyperK-Number In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23037.44003). 1834
1835
1836
230. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperOrder As Hyper Enumerations On Super Landmarks*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35646.56641). 1837
1838
1839
231. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Analogous By Hyper Visions Of SuperHyperOrder In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18030.48967). 1840
1841
1842
232. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperColoring As Hyper Categories On Super Neighbors*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13973.81121). 1843
1844
1845
233. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Relations By Hyper Identifications Of SuperHyperColoring In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34106.47047). 1846
1847
1848
234. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Contradiction By Hyper Detection of SuperHyperDefensive In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13397.09446). 1849
1850
1851
235. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDimension As Hyper Distinguishing On Super Distances*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31956.88961). 1852
1853
1854
236. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Locations By Hyper Differing Of SuperHyperDimension In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15179.67361). 1855
1856
1857
237. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDominating As Hyper Closing On Super Messy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21510.45125). 1858
1859
1860

238. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Missing By Hyper Searching Of SuperHyperDominating In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13121.84321). 1861
1862
1863
239. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperConnected As Hyper Group On Super Surge*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11758.69441). 1864
1865
1866
240. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Outbreak By Hyper Collections Of SuperHyperConnected In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31891.35367). 1867
1868
1869
241. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperTotal As Hyper Covering On Super Infections*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19360.87048). 1870
1871
1872
242. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Extremism By Hyper Treatments Of SuperHyperTotal In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32363.21286). 1873
1874
1875
243. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Isolation By Hyper Perfectness Of SuperHyperPerfect In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23266.81602). 1876
1877
1878
244. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperPerfect As Hyper Idealism On Super Vacancy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19911.37285). 1879
1880
1881
245. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperJoin As Hyper Separations On Super Sorts*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11050.90569). 1882
1883
1884
246. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super connections By Hyper disconnections Of SuperHyperJoin In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17761.79206). 1885
1886
1887
247. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Mixed-Devastations By Hyper Decisions Of SuperHyperDuality In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34953.52320). 1888
1889
1890
248. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition As (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDuality As Hyper Imaginations On Super Mixed-Illustrations*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33275.80161). 1891
1892
1893
249. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition As (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By Path SuperHyperColoring As Hyper Correction On Super Faults*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30182.50241). 1894
1895
1896
250. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Reflections By Hyper Rotations Of Path SuperHyperColoring In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33459.30243). 1897
1898
1899
251. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas As Hyper Deformations On Super Chains In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDensity*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13444.60806). 1900
1901
1902
252. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas As Hyper Ignorance By SuperHyperDensity On Super Resistances In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi:10.13140/RG.2.2.16800.05123). 1903
1904
1905

253. Henry Garrett, “*New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-VI*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29913.80482). 1906
1907
1908
1909
254. Henry Garrett, “*New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-V*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33269.24809). 1910
1911
1912
1913
255. Henry Garrett, “*New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-IV*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34946.96960). 1914
1915
1916
1917
256. Henry Garrett, “*A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-III*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.14814.31040). 1918
1919
1920
1921
257. Henry Garrett, “*A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-II*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15653.17125). 1922
1923
1924
1925
258. Henry Garrett, “*A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-I*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.25719.50089). 1926
1927
1928
1929
259. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Disruptions In Cancer’s Extreme Recognition As Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hyper Plans Called SuperHyperConnectivities*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29441.94562). 1930
1931
1932
1933
260. Henry Garrett, “*Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition As Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperConnectivities As Hyper Diagnosis On Super Mechanism*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17252.24968). 1934
1935
1936
261. Henry Garrett, “*Cancer’s Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By the Criteria of Eulerian and Hamiltonian Type-Sets As Hyper Modified Cycles On Super Mess*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.16652.59525). 1937
1938
1939
262. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian and Hamiltonian In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph On Super Interactions By Hyper Extensions of Cycles*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34583.24485). 1940
1941
1942
263. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth Type-Results on extreme SuperHyperGirth theory and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs Toward Cancer’s extreme Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010396 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0396.v1). 1943
1944
1945
1946
264. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Warns Hyper Landmark of neutrosophic SuperHyperGirth In Super Type-Versions of Cancer’s neutrosophic Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010395 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0395.v1). 1947
1948
1949
1950

265. Henry Garrett, “*The Constructions of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs on the Cancer’s Recognition in The Confrontation With Super Attacks In Hyper Situations By Implementing (Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in The Technical Approaches to Neutralize SuperHyperViews*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26240.51204). 1951-1955
266. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing As the Entrepreneurs on Cancer’s Recognitions To Fail Forcing Style As the Super Classes With Hyper Effects In The Background of the Framework is So-Called (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.12818.73925). 1956-1960
267. Henry Garrett, “*Super Actions On The Types of Hyper Levels In The Sensible Neutrosophic SuperHyperGirth On Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26836.88960). 1961-1964
268. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth Approaches on the Super Challenges on the Cancer’s Recognition In the Hyper Model of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36745.93289). 1965-1967
269. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010308 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0308.v1). 1968-1971
270. Henry Garrett, “*Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010282 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0282.v1). 1972-1975
271. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010267 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0267.v1).). 1976-1978
272. Henry Garrett, “*The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010265 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0265.v1). 1979-1984
273. Henry Garrett, “*Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010262, (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0262.v1). 1985-1988
274. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010240 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0240.v1). 1989-1992
275. Henry Garrett, “*Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010224, (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0224.v1). 1993-1996

276. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperMatching By (R-)Definitions And Polynomials To Monitor Cancer’s Recognition In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35061.65767). 1997
1998
1999
277. Henry Garrett, “*The Focus on The Partitions Obtained By Parallel Moves In The Cancer’s Extreme Recognition With Different Types of Extreme SuperHyperMatching Set and Polynomial on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18494.15680). 2000
2001
2002
2003
278. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer’s Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer’s Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32530.73922). 2004
2005
2006
2007
279. Henry Garrett, “*Indeterminacy On The All Possible Connections of Cells In Front of Cancer’s Attacks In The Terms of Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique on Cancer’s Recognition called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15897.70243). 2008
2009
2010
2011
280. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer’s Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer’s Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32530.73922). 2012
2013
2014
2015
281. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 2016
2017
2018
282. Henry Garrett, “*Perfect Directions Toward Idealism in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Forwarding Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30092.80004). 2019
2020
2021
283. Henry Garrett, “*Demonstrating Complete Connections in Every Embedded Regions and Sub-Regions in the Terms of Cancer’s Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClique*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23172.19849). 2022
2023
2024
2025
284. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 2026
2027
2028
2029
285. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1). 2030
2031
2032
2033
286. Henry Garrett, “*Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic Regions titled neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition modeled in the Form of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17385.36968). 2034
2035
2036
2037
287. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010044 2038
2039
2040

288. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, Preprints 2023, 2023010043 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0043.v1). 2041
2042
2043
289. Henry Garrett, “Using the Tool As (Neutrosophic) Failed SuperHyperStable To SuperHyperModel Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28945.92007). 2044
2045
2046
290. Henry Garrett, “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11447.80803). 2047
2048
2049
291. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well-SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35774.77123). 2050
2051
2052
292. Henry Garrett, “Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36141.77287). 2053
2054
2055
2056
293. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29430.88642). 2057
2058
2059
294. Henry Garrett, “Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11369.16487). 2060
2061
2062
2063
295. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances”, Preprints 2022, 2022120549 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0549.v1). 2064
2065
2066
296. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19380.94084). 2067
2068
2069
297. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses”, Preprints 2022, 2022120540 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0540.v1). 2070
2071
2072
2073
2074
298. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.14426.41923). 2075
2076
2077
2078
2079
299. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions”, Preprints 2022, 2022120500 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0500.v1). 2080
2081
2082
300. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20993.12640). 2083
2084
2085

301. Henry Garrett, “*Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120324 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0324.v1). 2086
2087
2088
2089
302. Henry Garrett, “*Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23123.04641). 2090
2091
2092
2093
303. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses*”, Preprints 2022, 2022110576 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202211.0576.v1). 2094
2095
2096
2097
304. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23324.56966). 2098
2099
2100
2101
305. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Neutrosophic Notions Concerning SuperHyperDominating and Neutrosophic SuperHyperResolving in SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29173.86244). 2102
2103
2104
306. Henry Garrett, “*Initial Material of Neutrosophic Preliminaries to Study Some Neutrosophic Notions Based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.25385.88160). 2105
2106
2107
2108
307. Henry Garrett, “Diamond search In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13525750). 2109
2110
308. Henry Garrett, “Triangle-free search In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13512157). 2111
2112
309. Henry Garrett, “Edge Cover In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13376543). 2113
2114
310. Henry Garrett, “Vertex Cover In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13294466). 2115
2116
311. Henry Garrett, “Burning Number In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12797511). 2117
2118
312. Henry Garrett, “Zero Forcing In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12691570). 2119
2120
313. Henry Garrett, “Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 6”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12651785). 2121
2122
314. Henry Garrett, “Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 5”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12214087). 2123
2124
315. Henry Garrett, “Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 4”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11876996). 2125
2126
316. Henry Garrett, “Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 3”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11529821). 2127
2128

317. Henry Garrett, “Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 2”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11398118). 2129
2130
318. Henry Garrett, “Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 1”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11106891). 2131
2132
319. Henry Garrett, “Perfect Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 3”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10946745). 2133
2134
320. Henry Garrett, “Perfect Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 2”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10909931). 2135
2136
321. Henry Garrett, “Perfect Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10871136). 2137
2138
322. Henry Garrett, “Stable Sequence In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10523307). 2139
2140
323. Henry Garrett, “Resolving Sequence In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10395711). 2141
2142
324. Henry Garrett, “Dominating Sequence In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10042973). 2143
2144
325. Henry Garrett, “Stable In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8210033). 2145
2146
326. Henry Garrett, “Reverse Connective Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206898). 2147
2148
327. Henry Garrett, “Equal Connective Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201378). 2149
2150
328. Henry Garrett, “Connective Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8194003). 2151
2152
329. Henry Garrett, “Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8113416). 2153
2154
330. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperPerfect Search In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8104880). 2155
2156
331. Henry Garrett, “Reverse Strict Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8092816). 2157
2158
332. Henry Garrett, “Unequal Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8090194). 2159
2160
333. Henry Garrett, “Strict Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8086310). 2161
2162
334. Henry Garrett, “Reverse Strict Connective In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8080167). 2163
2164
335. Henry Garrett, “Unequal Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8078574). 2165
2166
336. Henry Garrett, “Strict Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8076449). 2167
2168

337. Henry Garrett, “Reverse Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8072310). 2169
2170
338. Henry Garrett, “Equal Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8067469). 2171
2172
339. Henry Garrett, “Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8062076). 2173
2174
340. Henry Garrett, “Reverse Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8057817). 2175
2176
341. Henry Garrett, “Equal Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8052976). 2177
2178
342. Henry Garrett, “Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8051368). 2179
2180
343. Henry Garrett, “United Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8027488). 2181
2182
344. Henry Garrett, “Zero Forcing In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8020181). 2183
2184
345. Henry Garrett, “Matrix-Based In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7978921). 2185
2186
346. Henry Garrett, “Collections of Math II”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7943878). 2187
2188
347. Henry Garrett, “Dominating-Edges In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7943871). 2189
2190
348. Henry Garrett, “Edge-Gap In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7923786). 2191
2192
349. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7905287). 2193
2194
350. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904586). 2195
2196
351. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7874677). 2197
2198
352. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7857906). 2199
2200
353. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7856329). 2201
2202
354. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7854561). 2203
2204
355. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Type-Path-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7851893). 2205
2206
356. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Type-Path-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7848019). 2207
2208

- 357. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Type-Path-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7835063). 2209
2210
- 358. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Path-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7826705). 2211
2212
- 359. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Path-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7820680). 2213
2214
- 360. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Path-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7812750). 2215
2216
- 361. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7812142). 2217
2218
- 362. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7810394). 2219
2220
- 363. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7807782). 2221
2222
- 364. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804449). 2223
2224
- 365. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7793875). 2225
2226
- 366. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7792307). 2227
2228
- 367. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7790728). 2229
2230
- 368. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7787712). 2231
2232
- 369. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7783791). 2233
2234
- 370. Henry Garrett, “*Trace-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7780123). 2235
2236
- 371. Henry Garrett, “*Trace-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7773119). 2237
2238
- 372. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDuality*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7637762). 2239
2240
- 373. Henry Garrett, “*Trace-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7766174). 2241
2242
- 374. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7762232). 2243
2244
- 375. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7758601). 2245
2246
- 376. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7754661). 2247
2248

377. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7750995) . 2249
2250
378. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7749875). 2251
2252
379. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7747236). 2253
2254
380. Henry Garrett, “*Stable-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7742587). 2255
2256
381. Henry Garrett, “*Stable-Decompositions In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7738635). 2257
2258
382. Henry Garrett, “*Stable-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7734719). 2259
2260
383. Henry Garrett, “*Clique-Neighbors In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7730484). 2261
2262
384. Henry Garrett, “*Clique-Decompositions In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7730469). 2263
2264
385. Henry Garrett, “*Clique-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7722865). 2265
2266
386. Henry Garrett, “*Space In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7713563). 2267
2268
387. Henry Garrett, “*Space In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7709116). 2269
2270
388. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Connectivity In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7706415). 2271
2272
389. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Connectivity In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7706063). 2273
2274
390. Henry Garrett, “*Tree-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7701906). 2275
2276
391. Henry Garrett, “*Chord In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7700205). 2277
2278
392. Henry Garrett, “*(i,j)-Domination In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7694876). 2279
2280
393. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Domination In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7679410). 2281
2282
394. Henry Garrett, “*K-Domination In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7675982). 2283
2284
395. Henry Garrett, “*K-Number In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7672388). 2285
2286
396. Henry Garrett, “*Order In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7668648). 2287
2288

397. Henry Garrett, “*Coloring In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7662810). 2289
2290
398. Henry Garrett, “*Dimension In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7659162). 2291
2292
399. Henry Garrett, “*Cancer In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653233). 2293
2294
400. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperWheel*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653204). 2295
2296
401. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperMultipartite*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653142). 2297
2298
402. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperBipartite*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653117). 2299
2300
403. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperStar*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653089). 2301
2302
404. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7651687). 2303
2304
405. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperPath*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7651619). 2305
2306
406. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDomination*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7651439). 2307
2308
407. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7650729). 2309
2310
408. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperConnected*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7647868). 2311
2312
409. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperTotal*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7647017). 2313
2314
410. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperPerfect*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7644894). 2315
2316
411. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperJoin*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7641880). 2317
2318
412. Henry Garrett, “*Path SuperHyperColoring*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7632923). 2319
2320
413. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDensity*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7623459). 2321
2322
414. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnectivities*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7606416). 2323
2324
415. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperConnectivities*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7606416). 2325
2326
416. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperConnectivities*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7606404). 2327
2328

417. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7580018). 2329
2330
418. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7580018). 2331
2332
419. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7580018). 2333
2334
420. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7579929). 2335
2336
421. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563170). 2337
2338
422. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563164). 2339
2340
423. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563160). 2341
2342
424. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563160). 2343
2344
425. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563160). 2345
2346
426. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7557063). 2347
2348
427. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7557009). 2349
2350
428. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7539484). 2351
2352
429. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2353
2354
430. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2355
2356
431. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2357
2358
432. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7574952). 2359
2360
433. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7574992). 2361
2362
434. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523357). 2363
2364
435. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523357). 2365
2366
436. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2367
2368

- 437. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2369
2370
- 438. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2371
2372
- 439. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2373
2374
- 440. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2375
2376
- 441. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2377
2378
- 442. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7497450). 2379
2380
- 443. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7497450). 2381
2382
- 444. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2383
2384
- 445. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2385
2386
- 446. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2387
2388
- 447. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2389
2390
- 448. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2391
2392
- 449. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2393
2394
- 450. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7539484). 2395
2396
- 451. Henry Garrett, “*Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2397
2398
- 452. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523357). 2399
2400
- 453. Henry Garrett, “*Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2401
2402
- 454. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2403
2404
- 455. Henry Garrett, “*Failed SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7497450). 2405
2406
- 456. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2407
2408

457. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi:
10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2409
2410
458. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi:
10.5281/zenodo.7480110). 2411
2412
459. Henry Garrett, “*Neut. SuperHyperEdges*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi:
10.5281/zenodo.7378758). 2413
2414
460. Henry Garrett, “*Beyond Neutrosophic Graphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi:
10.5281/zenodo.6320305). 2415
2416
461. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Duality*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi:
10.5281/zenodo.6677173). 2417
2418